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THE CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF INTERNET COMMUNICATION

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Introduction. Today, the global computer network has become one of the main means of communication between people and the main source of information. The Internet is an association of computer networks with common standards that allow messages to be sent from any Central Computer (or host) on the same network to any other host. The first steps towards the emergence of the Internet were taken by telegraph operators in the late 1800s, who used Morse code for long-distance messages. Internet communication has come a long way since its inception in the early 20th century. This was followed by telephone calls, which allowed people to communicate with each other across geographical boundaries. These technologies eventually evolved into email, which allowed users to send messages back and forth between computers.

The Internet began as an experimental network in the United States in the 1960s among the military, and soon expanded to include federal, state, university, business, and private users. Today, it is the largest computer network in the world, with the help of which it provides many services and enables communication between people through e-mails, discussion groups and digital pages on any topic. The Internet was originally created for pragmatic purposes, but now it has become a social phenomenon that unites representatives of different mentalities, cultures and nationalities.

The history of the Internet is constantly changing. Internet communication research began in the mid-1990s, and by the 20th century philosophy, sociology,

actively developing in the field of psychology, linguistics and other related sciences. Population research is becoming more active due to the rapid growth of the popularity of Internet communication among It has been studied by sociologists since the Internet appeared. The Internet is considered both a global and national communication tool, a source and distributor of new ideas, views, interpretations, and it is a new social environment that is expanding more and more. The Internet is a new social environment that expands the understanding of human interaction in the information technology society.

First, the purpose of the Internet is to provide users with various information provided, but today communication between people is virtual has become the leading function of the space, and at the same time, intergroup communication has become a unique means of communication in social networks and blogs. In this regard, a number of definitions appear, in which the Internet is considered in terms of its function in society. Internet communication is a special type of communication carried out through a computer and the Global Internet. Includes this and features of mass communication, i.e. communication involving many people; internal and group communication. It should be noted that "electronic communication", "virtual communication", "computer communication" are synonyms. Computer communication has led to the widespread use of the word "virtual". In computer terminology, virtual means "not really existing, imaginary". The virtual world does not actually exist, but it appears under certain conditions, in this case, through the influence of the computer on the human emotions, which gives him the illusion of immersion in this world. Computer communication is a system in which reality (that is, the material-symbolic existence of people) is completely embedded in the non-external world. [Castells 2000] concludes: "Virtual communication is loom, communication with an unknown group of imaginary interlocutors. Virtual communication fills reality and appears in our minds."

According to N.G. Asmus, in virtual communication, a person himself creates information and knowledge and uses the concept of "text" as a unique, vivid, carnival-like phenomenon in linguistic design [Asmus 2005]. Communication between virtual persons is established through texts, that is, there is no direct physical contact in computer communication between people. Therefore, the text in the virtual space takes the status of a universal and unique means of information exchange. Thus, the global Internet has become the main source of knowledge and information exchange, and has created a new type of communication - Internet communication.

According to M. Yu. Sidorova, Internet diaries or blogs are interactions in a separate global network and are a set of interrelated blogs, covers the concept of the understood "blogosphere". The Blagosphere is a separate communication environment,

the Internet where everyone has the opportunity to create a virtual identity and construct their own identity, including gender, environment. In addition, the "blogosphere" is two mutually exclusive elements - language expression, content and pragmatic intentions at the level of simplification and complexification, as well as active norms of literary language and colloquial speech.

Communication is constantly evolving, some people are used to seeing their friend's online avatar as their face. Communication with friends and more desire to share with near-strangers than to create memories. Due to all these factors, the range of Internet users is very wide and constantly growing, which has fundamentally important consequences for society and culture. According to researchers, the Internet creates a new way of organizing people's lives and is a new socio-cultural institution. The Internet creates a new world parallel to the real world, this world is called the electronic world; and even the seventh, "electronic" continent. This world has its own norms, rules, etiquette and language, and a fundamentally new type of communication - Internet communication - is emerging. Most scientific definitions of the word "communication" or "communication" refer to the idea of communicating something to someone or sharing knowledge. It should be noted that these two terms are used interchangeably. For example,

1) Communication is the interaction of people, the content of which is the process of joint activity to establish a comfortable relationship for mutual knowledge and exchange of information through various means of communication.

2) "Communication is the process of changing the relationship in which information is stored by the individuals involved in the interaction."

The specific features of Internet communication exactly match the features of mass communication that includes the Internet. N. Bogomolova distinguishes the following main features of mass communication: the use of technical means in communication, the involvement of large social groups, the non-binding response of feedback, the fact that communicators are strangers in real life and separated from each other while remaining anonymous.

Often, at events or parties, guests are connected to their smartphones, busy texting or sending messages, and no one listens carefully to others, participates in the conversation or communicates. As the generations enter the social age, social media is preferred among the youth will remain a form of communication. However, this change affects their ability to communicate properly with their peers starts.

Sh. H. Shahobiddinova and Sh.Kh. In Yuldasheva's article "Some comments on Internet communication and its research", the positive and negative aspects of Internet communication were considered and the above opinions about the positive aspects of

Internet communication were confirmed. It is interesting to note that the disadvantages are almost indistinguishable from the achievements, in particular:

1. Non-restriction in space: through the Internet, a person in any part of the world can communicate and turn the flow of communication to someone who is not acceptable to you, and because he knows that he will go unpunished, there are cases of crossing the border.

2. Not being limited in time: one of the main factors leading to Internet addiction. Communicating at any time has brought great changes to the many millennia of communication experience of mankind. The fact that it is not necessary to take into account the time of the interlocutor, the possibility of connecting to several directions at the same time allows communication to continue almost continuously. There is no doubt that this will have a negative impact on the social and household characteristics, health and mental state of Internet users.

3. Anonymity. Concealing one's identity and describing oneself as desired makes virtual communication unpredictable and unprotected compared to actual communication. Entering into a conversation without knowing who the interlocutor really is makes the techniques acquired during actual communication almost ineffective.

4. Voluntary. The fact that the dialogue can be started and ended at the discretion of one party is also considered as a special achievement. It is enough to send replicas to voluntarily start communication. It is also optional for the other party not to see it and not to send a reply.

5. Globality. The fact that national, gender, and class boundaries, which are usual in actual communication, are almost non-existent in virtual communication is a blow to the national mentality. It is no secret that communication habits and manners, which are part of national identity, are gradually giving way to elements of popular culture.

6. Threats to security are also taking new forms in virtual communication methods. As noted above, anonymity makes communication unpredictable and unprotected. The limitation of paralinguistic tools (tone of voice, eye gaze, skin color, hand movements) available for assessing the interlocutor in face-to-face communication makes the dialog process effective in normal forms of communication almost useless for diagnosis and defense mechanism.

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